

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

D5.2 Report On the Procedure for the Capacity Building and the Selection of the Main Hot Spots

VERSION 1

Acknowledgment: This project is part of the PRIMA Programme supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 1923.

Disclaimer: The content of this publication is solely responsibility of the authors and it does not represent the view of the PRIMA Foundation.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7031385](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7031385)

Project Information

Project Title	Innovative and sustainable groundwater management in the Mediterranean		
Project Acronym	InTheMED	Grant Agreement Number	1923
Program	Horizon 2020		
Type of Action	Water RIA – Research and innovation Action		
Start Date	March 1, 2020	Duration	36 months
Project Coordinator	Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Spain		
Consortium	<p>Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Spain</p> <p>Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung (UFZ), Germany</p> <p>Università degli Studi di Parma (UNIPR), Italy</p> <p>Boğaziçi Üniversitesi (BU), Turkey</p> <p>Centre de Recherches et des Technologies des Eaux (CERTE), Tunisie</p> <p>Technical University of Crete (TUC), Greece</p> <p>Associação do Instituto Superior Técnico para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento (IST-ID), Portugal</p>		

Document Information

Deliverable Number	D5.2	Deliverable Name	Report On the Procedure for the Capacity Building and the Selection of the Main Hot Spots	
Work Package number	WP2	Work Package Title	Innovative Remediation Strategies in the MED	
Due Date	Contractual	August 31, 2022	Actual	August 29, 2022
Version Number	Version 1			
Deliverable Type	Report (R)	Dissemination Level	Public (PU)	
Authors	Hanene Akrouit Hatem Baccouche Lobna Mansouri Ahmed Ghrabi Thouraya Mellah			
Co-authors	Janire Uribe-Asarta Vanessa A. Godoy J. Jaime Gómez-Hernández Emmanouil Varouchakis George Karatzas Irem Daloglu İzel Uygur Ali K. Saysel Nadim Copty Leonardo Azevedo			
Reviewers	All			

Document History

Version	Date	Stage	Reviewed by
0.1	23/06/2022	Creation	Hatem Baccouche
0.2	24/06/2022	Review	Hanene Akrouit Lobna Mansouri Ahmed Ghrabi
0.3	01/07/2022	First draft	Hanene Akrouit Hatem Baccouche

0.4	19/07/2022	Modifications/Enrichment	Irem Daloglu İzel Uygur Ali K. Saysel Nadim Copty
0.5	19/07/2022	Modifications/Enrichment/Review	Irem Daloglu İzel Uygur Ali K. Saysel Nadim Copty Janire Uribe-Asarta Vanessa A. Godoy J. Jaime Gómez-Hernández Hatem Baccouche
0.6	20/07/2022	Review/Modifications	Hatem Baccouche
0.7	21/07/2022	Modifications/Enrichment	Janire Uribe-Asarta Vanessa A. Godoy J. Jaime Gómez-Hernández
0.8	22/07/2022	Review	Hatem Baccouche
0.9	22/07/2022	Review/Modifications	Hatem Baccouche
0.10	25/07/2022	Review/Modifications	Janire Uribe-Asarta Vanessa A. Godoy J. Jaime Gómez-Hernández
0.11	26/07/2022	Review	Hatem Baccouche
0.12	30/07/2022	Modifications/Enrichment	Emmanouil Varouchakis George Karatzas
0.13	01/08/2022	Review	Hatem Baccouche
0.14	03/08/2022	Modifications/Enrichment/Review	İzel Uygur Irem Daloglu Ali K. Saysel Nadim Copty Hatem Baccouche
0.15	08/08/2022	Modifications/Enrichment/Review	Lobna Mansouri Hatem Baccouche İzel Uygur
0.16	12/08/2022	Modifications/Enrichment/Review	Leonardo Azevedo
1	15/08/2022	Review - Final version	CERTE Team

Table of Contents

Project Information.....	2
Document Information	3
Document History.....	3
Table of Contents.....	5
List of Tables	7
List of Figures	8
Glossary.....	9
Executive Summary.....	10
1. Overview.....	11
2. Selection of main hotspots and procedure for the capacity building.....	12
2.1. Problem identification and selection of main hotspots.....	12
2.1.1. Case studies	12
2.1.1.1. Grombalia, Tunisia case study	12
2.1.1.1.1. Problem identification	12
2.1.1.1.2. Selection of main hotspots	14
2.1.1.2. Requena-Utiel, Spain case study	15
2.1.1.2.1. Survey	15
2.1.1.2.2. Problem identification	22
2.1.1.2.3. Selection of main hotspots	24
2.1.1.3. Castro Verde, Portugal Case Study	24
2.1.1.3.1. Survey	24
2.1.1.3.1.1. Problem identification	45
2.1.1.3.1.2. Selection of main hotspots	45
2.1.1.4. Tympaki, Greece Case Study	46
2.1.1.4.1. Survey	46
2.1.1.4.2. Problem identification	52
2.1.1.4.3. Selection of main hotspots.....	52
2.1.1.5. Konya, Turkey Case Study.....	52
2.1.1.5.1. Survey	52
2.1.1.5.2. Problem identification.....	63
2.1.1.5.3. Selection of main hotspots.....	64

2.2. Procedure for capacity building	64
2.2.1. Local stakeholders mapping.....	64
2.2.2. Selection procedure	67
3. References	72

List of Tables

Table 1. Cases Studies Characteristics.....	12
Table 2. Mine Water Management System.....	30
Table 3. Substances included in List I.	33
Table 4. Substances included in List II	33
Table 5. Total volume of effluent discharged into the Oeiras River between 2013 and 2015 .36	
Table 6. Monitoring program of treated industrial effluent at SOMINCOR’s laboratories.....	36
Table 7. Monitoring program of the recirculated water from the IRCL at SOMINCOR’s laboratories	37
Table 8. Monitoring program of treated industrial effluent at external laboratories	38
Table 9. Monitoring program of the environment receiving discharge from the mining complex.....	39
Table 10. Monitoring program of groundwater resources.....	39
Table 11. Maximum and mean values of the monitored parameters at stations 548/25 and 572/16 of the groundwater quality monitoring network for the period between April 2015 to March 2021	42
Table 12. Maximum and mean values of the monitored parameters at station 28J/02 (Oeiras River) of the surface water quality monitoring network for the period between April 2015 to March 2021	43
Table 13. Turkish Statistical Institute data from 2020.....	58
Table 14. Main local polluter/userlist, Grombalia Case study	64
Table 15. Main local user list, Requena-Utiel Case study	65
Table 16. Main local user list, Tympaki Case study	66
Table 17. Main local user list, Konya Case study	67
Table 18. User’s engagement assessment	68
Table 19. Selected candidates	70

List of Figures

Figure 1. Grombalia study area	14
Figure 2. Groundwater quality monitoring points location in Requena-Utiel, Spain.....	18
Figure 3. Nitrate observations at Requena-Utiel, Spain	18
Figure 4. WWTPs location, population equivalent and influent at Requena-Utiel, Spain	20
Figure 5. Location of Neves-Corvo mining site in southern Portugal	26
Figure 6. Neves-Corvo mining complex.....	27
Figure 7. Groundwater status classification	32
Figure 8. Locations of stations.....	41
Figure 9. Sample analysis from 39 different streams in the basin.....	62

Glossary

BOD	Biochemical Oxygen Demand
BOD5	Five-day Biochemical Oxygen Demand
COD	Chemical Oxygen Demand
cm	Centimetre
EU	European
Ha	Hectare
Hr	Hour
Km	Kilometre
L	Litre
M	Metre
m³	Cubic metre
mg	Milligram
Mm³	Million cubic metre
MLPC	Main Local Polluter Candidate
N/A	Not available – Not applicable – No answer
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
PRIMA	Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area
WHO	World Health Organization
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant
μS	Microsiemens

Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects

The current document, Deliverable D5.2, is part of Task 5.2 “Capacity building on sustainable integrated water management” and aims at strengthening stakeholder capacity at the regional level, contribute to the empowerment of water related institutions, and to prepare a regional roster of experts from the MED countries who can deal successfully with sustainable water management issues in the region.

1. Overview

The current document, Deliverable D5.2, is part of Task 5.2 “Capacity building on sustainable integrated water management” and targets reinforcing stakeholder capacity at the regional level, contribute to the strengthening of water related organizations, and to prepare a regional roster of experts from the MED countries who can deal successfully with sustainable water management issues in the region. There will be a call for the interested stakeholders identified in Task 5.1, who will be engaged in a social learning process for the design of new water management consistent with the 4R principle (Reduce, Recycle, Reuse and Recover) and to implement the best available technologies for an efficient treatment of their effluents. Special attention will be put on reusing treated wastewater as an alternative source of irrigation, in-situ reuse in industrial processes, and aquifer recharge. The results will be disseminated through participatory interactive sessions (Living Labs) in close collaboration with WP4 and all case-study partners. Attention will be put on the socio-economic aspects (WP4) and (WP6).

The participating partners filled out surveys prepared by CERTE Team to acquire preliminary information on main problems, hotspots, and the existing remediation strategies. The data collected for the selected case studies are presented in the following sections.

2. Selection of main hotspots and procedure for the capacity building

2.1. Problem identification and selection of main hotspots

2.1.1. Case studies

The fundamental characteristics of the five study sites are summed up in Table 1. The case studies show different contrasts in size, populace, and area of the groundwater basins. The basin sizes range from 363 to 62,000 km² and the populace from 30,000 to 3,000,000 individuals. The climatic properties are additionally different with mean yearly precipitation going from 356.5 to 440 mm and mean yearly temperature from 12 to 22 °C (Table 1).

Table 1. Cases Studies Characteristics

Characteristics	Requena-Utiel, Spain	Tympaki, Greece	Castro Verde, Portugal	Grombalia, Tunisia	Konya, Turkey
Size (km ²)	1360	55	30	363	62000
Population	30,000	25,000	7,276	201,836	~3,000,000
Location	Inland	Coastal	Inland	Coastal	Inland
Mean P & T (mm y ¹ /°C)	440/13	500/15	567/16	356,5/22	387/12
Principal groundwater users	Agriculture, urban	Agriculture	Urban, mining	Agriculture, industry, tourism	Agriculture, urban
Overexploited	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Groundwater pollution	No	Nitrate, salinity	Mine wastes	Nitrate, salinity	Nitrate, salinity

2.1.1.1. Grombalia, Tunisia case study

2.1.1.1.1. Problem identification

The Grombalia basin is undermined by anthropogenic pressures, for instance, overexploitation of groundwater resources. This aquifer represents the principal source of water supply. In 2009, the annual exploitation in the region was assessed at 250 Mm³/year.

A rising pattern was kept in the amounts of water removed from the shallow and deep aquifer. Agricultural and industrial activities in the study area utilize huge amounts of water which is removed basically from the deep aquifer. Indeed, industries and farmers use deep aquifer in citrus irrigation especially in Beni Khalled, Menzel Bouzelfa, and Soliman regions because of its good quality. Simultaneously, an expansion in the quantity of unlawful wells is disturbing. 600 wells are the total number of illegal wells installed until the end of 2017 assessed by the directorate general of water resources with typical yearly volume of 6000 m³/well [1]. The Grombalia aquifer (Figure 1) is challenged by degradation in water quality and saltwater intrusion as well. The mix of excess irrigation, over-fertilization, and industrial discharge in the hydrographic ecosystem has prompted injurious consequences on the environment through surface water contamination and expanded Grombalia groundwater pollution. The TDS values of groundwater range from 0.75 to 5.6 g/l [2]. As per WHO guidelines [3,] 50 mg/L is defined as the nitrate concentration threshold for drinking water. Notwithstanding, the average nitrate concentration of Grombalia groundwater is around 139 mg/L which is higher than the above threshold value [4]. On the other hand, the deep aquifer is less dirtied by nitrate than the shallow aquifer with nitrate concentrations ranging between 7.3 and 38.5 mg/L [4] which stayed well beneath the the WHO limit. Indeed, the shallow aquifer is more likely exposed to the anthropogenic activities which become a growing concern and urges to provide tailored solutions for sustainable management of water resources that support social and economic development while preserving the environment.

Figure 1. Grombalia study area

2.1.1.1.2. Selection of main hotspots

Regarding the Tunisian case study, the project team decided to focus on the industrial activity which is impactful and well developed and diversified in the study area with about 250 companies distributed in four industrial zones that cover more than 100 ha. The industries that present major problems in water - management, whether quantitatively or qualitatively, and which directly or indirectly affect the local water cycle have been identified and essentially belong to the textile, agri-food, leather and tanning sectors.

2.1.1.2. Requena-Utiel, Spain case study

2.1.1.2.1. Survey

Survey questions

Survey to acquire preliminary information on the Nitrate pollution

Site Name: Requena-Utiel, Spain

1. Name and email of contact person in the project team
Name:
email:
2. According to you, what are the sources of water nitrate pollution in Requena-Utiel?
3. How nitrate contamination affected the groundwater in Requena-Utiel?
4. Is there contamination of surface water by nitrates?
5. If so, what is its origin according to you?
6. Could you please map the pollution Hotspots?
7. What type of crops/plants do farmers grow in Requena-Utiel?
8. What type of fertilizer do they use most?
9. What is the nitrate concentration in the fertilizers used?
10. What is the frequency of the use of fertilizers with high nitrate concentration (in time, per crop)?
11. Do farmers of study area spread livestock manure (or liquid manure) during their agricultural activities?
12. According to you, is there an excess in livestock manure spreading?
13. How many waste water treatment plants (WWTP) are there in the study area?
14. What is the volume of treated water in Requena-Utiel?
15. Where do they discharge their rejections?
16. Have you analyzed the water released by the WWTP? Do they meet the standards?
17. Is there a hydraulic connection between the water table and surface water (rivers, ..)?
18. If so, what is the type of connection? (contribution of groundwater to rivers, groundwater recharge by rivers, ..)
19. In your opinion, could the nitrate contamination be of domestic origin?

20. Is the whole urban area connected to the sanitation network?
 21. If not, where is the urban wastewater discharged?
 22. Are industries connected to the sanitation network?
 23. If not, where do they discharge their wastewater?
 24. Could you list the existing industrial activities in the study area? Could you map it please?
 25. Have you analyzed the water released by the industrial units? Do they meet the standards?
 26. Is there a eutrophication problem in the study area?
 27. What are the main “In situ remediation technologies” used in Requena-Utiel basin relative to nitrate pollution?
 28. Are there any conducted cost-benefit analyses relating to environmental impacts of nitrate pollution in Requena-Utiel?
 29. Could you please provide us the water quality analyses (recently sampled on site) relative to groundwater and surface water?
 30. Is it possible to send us 10 L of each water sample from each sampling point?
-

Survey Results

Site Name: Requena-Utiel, Spain

1. Name and email of contact person in the project team

Name: Janire Uribe Asarta

email: j.uribeasarta@gmail.com

2. According to you, what are the sources of water nitrate pollution in Requena-Utiel?

Stockbreeding and agriculture.

3. How nitrate contamination affected the groundwater in Requena-Utiel?

Although the quality control network of the Júcar Water Authority has registered values that are very close to or even exceed the limit allowed by law of 50 mg/L of nitrates [5], the Júcar Water Authority does not consider the Requena-Utiel and Cabrillas-Malacara aquifers

affected by nitrate contamination and declare that the qualitative status of both aquifers is favorable.

4. Is there contamination of surface water by nitrates?

The Júcar Water Authority has demonstrated the decrease in the quality of surface waters associated with groundwater due to chemical changes.

5. If so, what is its origin according to you?

Groundwater discharges.

6. Could you please map the pollution Hotspots?

Figures 2 and 3 show the nitrate values measured throughout 2008 and 2020 for the Requena-Utiel groundwater mass. In 2008, the control point 08.133.CA001 registers values much higher than the threshold, which may be due to the area it samples; it is located near the city of Utiel and in an area of great agricultural activity. A decrease can be noted in 2009; however, up-to-date data for that particular site are not available to define its current status. Nonetheless, the city council of Utiel has reported that one of the wells used for the public supply to the city has recently shown nitrate concentrations above 50 mg/L (threshold) [5]. The values of the rest of the control points indicate a good chemical state, although as of 2020, values close to the threshold appear. The nitrate values for the Cabrillas-Malacara groundwater mass are much lower than the threshold, indicating a good chemical state.

8. What type of fertilizer do they use most?

We do not know the type of fertilizer that each farmer uses, although many of the cultivated hectares they use ecological techniques.

9. What is the nitrate concentration in the fertilizers used?

We do not know the nitrate concentration in the fertilizers.

10. What is the frequency of the use of fertilizers with high nitrate concentration (in time, per crop)?

According to what some farmers commented, they apply water and fertilizers simultaneously through the irrigation system. Irrigation is carried out, in a generalized way among farmers, from June to September, with the most intense irrigation being in the months of July and August.

11. Do farmers of study area spread livestock manure (or liquid manure) during their agricultural activities?

No.

12. According to you, is there an excess in livestock manure spreading?

No.

13. How many wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) are there in the study area?

Six WWTP, their location is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. WWTPs location, population equivalent and influent at Requena-Utiel, Spain

14. What is the volume of treated water in Requena-Utiel?

Approximately 7,158 m³/day.

15. Where do they discharge their rejections?

The effluent is discharged into rivers near the WWTPs that flow into the Magro river.

16. Have you analyzed the water released by the WWTP? Do they meet the standards?

Egevasa, the company that operates the WWTPs, is in charge of performing the quality analysis of the discharge water.

The quality data (suspended solids, BOD₅, COD, total nitrate and total phosphorus) are not public, but must comply with the standards by law.

17. Is there a hydraulic connection between the water table and surface water (rivers, ..)?

Yes, there is an aquifer-river connection with the Magro river.

18. If so, what is the type of connection? (Contribution of groundwater to rivers, groundwater recharge by rivers, ..)

According to IGME-DGA [7] all the rivers in the study area are winners. Martinez's study [8] indicates that after the intense pumping began, the river-aquifer connection ceased to be

stable along the Magro River and there were continuous connections and disconnections, which caused the volume contributed by the aquifer to the river to decrease.

19. In your opinion, could the nitrate contamination be of domestic origin?

It is quite unlikely.

20. Is the whole urban area connected to the sanitation network?

No, some villages, with few inhabitants and far from the main urban centers, are not connected to the WWTPs, they have septic tanks.

21. If not, where is the urban wastewater discharged?

-

22. Are industries connected to the sanitation network?

Yes.

23. If not, where do they discharge their wastewater?

-

24. Could you list the existing industrial activities in the study area? Could you map it please?

- San Benedetto water bottling company,
- Multiple wineries, among them we can highlight: Vegalfaro, Vereda Real, Coviñas and Iranzo,

25. Have you analyzed the water released by the industrial units? Do they meet the standards?

No, we have not analyzed them.

26. Is there a eutrophication problem in the study area?

No.

27. What are the main “In situ remediation technologies” used in Requena-Utiel basin relative to nitrate pollution?

The aquifer is not contaminated by nitrates, so there are no “in situ remediation technologies” used in Requena-Utiel basin relative to nitrate pollution.

28. Are there any conducted cost-benefit analyses relating to environmental impacts of nitrate pollution in Requena-Utiel?

No.

29. Could you please provide us the water quality analyses (recently sampled on site) relative to groundwater and surface water?

Not possible.

30. Is it possible to send us 10 L of each water sample from each sampling point?

No.

2.1.1.2.2. Problem identification

In the Spanish study case, numerous pumping began in the 1980s and they have been increasing since 2001, especially because farmers switched from rainfed crops to irrigated crops. The Requena-Utiel and Cabrillas-Malacara aquifers are the main sources of water supply for farmers in this region, 1,059 wells out of a total of 1,275 are used for irrigation. Moreover, these aquifers are exploited for urban, industrial and livestock uses. The abusive exploitation of the aquifer has caused the water level series to show a progressive decrease and the aquifer storage balance to be negative, which indicates the emptying of the aquifer. This steady drop in the water table may have caused other issues in surface water resources that depend on groundwater. The river-aquifer flow exchange between the Magro river and the aquifer has diminished, which may be due to the loss of aquifer storage. A stream flow depletion in the Magro river has been noted and consequently, the inflows to the Forata reservoir have been lowered, which has led to supply problems for its users, predominantly farmers.

Thus, the Hydrological Plan of the Júcar Water Authority for the 2015-2021 term [6] declares the Requena-Utiel groundwater mass in bad quantitative state and remediation strategies were defined.

The primary strategy is the creation, in December 2016, of the Exploitation Plan for the Requena-Utiel groundwater mass [9]. The Exploitation Plan, which was reviewed and approved in December 2020 [10], aims to achieve an efficient management and planning to ensure a reliable service to users and to restore the good quantitative status of the

groundwater mass. The objective of this Plan is to establish the criteria for the distribution of the reserve established in the 2015-2021 Hydrological Plan [6]. In addition, new water concessions requested after the entry into force of the 2015-2021 Plan will not be accepted. Finally, a variable allocation is established depending on whether the year is wet, medium or dry, considering antecedent precipitation.

Since the active participation of the stakeholders is fundamental to ensure an efficient management and planning as aimed in the Exploitation Plan, the Spanish team of the PRIMA project eGROUNDWATER, in cooperation with the Spanish team of the InTheMED project, organized on the 4th of March 2022 a living lab for the study area. The purpose of this living lab was to arrive at a diagnosis of the problem of unsustainable use of groundwater in the region and brainstorm about possible measures, technological needs, and the design of tools to achieve the common goal of continuing exploiting the aquifer. Among the attendees there were various stakeholders who play a significant role in the management of the Requena-Utiel aquifer, including environmental technicians, individual users, irrigation community representatives, researchers, Requena and Utiel City Hall personnel and an ONG member. The main strength of the participatory workshop was the stakeholders' intense participation and their willingness to collaborate with the management of the aquifer. This participatory and dynamic space highlighted the need for more means of dissemination about the condition of the aquifer, followed by hydrogeological information transmitted in a didactic way.

Prior to the living lab, the Spanish team carried out individual interviews with the stakeholders that allowed them to meet the users of the aquifer individually and learn about their concerns and opinions. The questionnaires included questions about their use of the resource, the quantity and quality of the water, and their vision of the governance of the aquifer. In relation to the quality of the water, only one user commented that in one of its wells, located near the Magro River, 47mg/L of nitrate was detected, an alarming value considering that the Spanish legal limit is 50mg/L [5]. Furthermore, the groundwater quality network of the Requena-Utiel and Cabrillas-Malacara aquifers is scarce and out of date, making it difficult to perform a study. Nevertheless, the Júcar Water Authority does not

consider that either of the two aquifers is affected by nitrate contamination and declares that the qualitative status of both aquifers is favourable.

2.1.1.2.3. Selection of main hotspots

Since nitrate contamination of groundwater is not a current problem defined by the Júcar Water Authority, the study of the Spanish case study is focused only on the quantitative aspects, which are mainly concerned to the depletion of the water table and the emptying of the aquifers. The Spanish project team decided to focus on agricultural activity, which is the most prominent groundwater user, with progressive growth throughout the last decades, mainly from the year 2001.

The main hotspots that present major quantitative problems in water management and directly or indirectly affect the local water cycle have been identified and essentially belong to vine cultivation, produced throughout the whole territory of the aquifer.

2.1.1.3. Castro Verde, Portugal Case Study

2.1.1.3.1. Survey

Survey questions

Survey to acquire preliminary information on the mining activities remediation strategies

Site Name: Castro Verde case study, Portugal.

1. Name and email of contact person in the project team
2. What is the processing practice used by mining activities in the Castro Verde area? (ie. The mining process, mineral processing operations, mine dewatering, seepage of contaminated leachates, flooding of mine workings, and discharge of untreated waters, ...)
3. What are the impacts of mining on water resources in the Castro Verde area?
4. What are the characteristics of Mine Waters? What are the main types of Mine Water Pollution in this area? Which Mine water treatment systems are used?
5. How important are groundwater resources for mine production processes? What is the estimated volume of water needed for the mining activities in the Castro Verde area?

6. How does groundwater quality degradation arise from mining activity in the Castro Verde area?
7. Are there any specific Mine water regulation/standards issued by the Portuguese / local authorities?
8. What are the Impacts mining activities on local groundwater drainage, flow, and discharge? In what ways do mining activities interact with groundwater systems?
9. What are the impacts of mining on physical hydrogeology in the Castro Verde area (i.e.Focus on the following topics: The types of mines which exist (deep, surface), their methods of working and the geometry of voids which they produce? Mine wastes: their origins and nature. The implications of the above for physical hydrogeology of mined ground,
10. Can mine drainage operations be an important source of water-supply in the Castro Verde area?
11. What is being done /What measures have been put in place by Castro Verde local authorities to mitigate impacts of mining on groundwater?
12. What are the main “In situ remediation technologies” used in this basin (there may be one technology or there many/combined i.e.Permeable Reactive Barrier Systems, Wetland Systems...? Non-conventional wastewater treatment?) What is the volume of treated water?
13. Are there any modelling mine water flow or geochemical processes controlling/monitoring mine water pollution?
14. Are there any conducted cost benefit analyses relating to environmental impacts of mining activities, in the Castro Verde area? (e.g. wastewater management, water use, remediation and compliance costs, monitoring)
15. What are the impacts of mining water pollution on people living and farming activities in the Castro Verde area?
16. Please provide water quality analyses (recently sampled on site) relative to groundwater and surface water?

N.B Please send as 10L of water from each sampling site.

Survey results

Obs: This survey was written considering the Environmental Impact Studies, Monitoring Reports, and National Management Water Plan for the area under study, available at the Portuguese Environmental Agency for public consultation. So far, the communication with the owner of the mining concession (SOMINCOR) has not been effective. SOMINCOR holds all the data, but despite reporting their activities to the Portuguese Environmental Agency, not all information is available. Therefore, this survey might have information that is not up to date.

1. Site Name (Description and Location)

The Portuguese case study relies within a mine concession named Neves-Corvo and operated by the mining company Lundin-SOMINCOR. The Neves-Corvo polymetallic base metal deposit is located within the western part of the world-class Iberian Pyrite Belt of southern Spain and Portugal. The mine is situated in the Alentejo province, which is located in southern region of Portugal, and about 15km to the southeast of the town of Castro Verde (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Location of Neves-Corvo mining site in southern Portugal (Google Earth credit)

2. Name and email of contact person in the project team

Name: Leonardo Azevedo

Email: leonardo.azevedo@tecnico.ulisboa.pt

3. What is the processing practice used by mining activities in the Castro Verde area? (ie. The mining process, mineral processing operations, mine dewatering, seepage of contaminated leachates, flooding of mine workings, and discharge of untreated waters, ...)

Neves-Corvo has been developed as an underground operation, exploiting several polymetallic sulphide orebodies [12]. The mining complex is composed by two main areas: the Industrial Area and the Cerro do Lobo Tailings Installation (IRCL) Figure 6 [11].

Figure 6. Neves-Corvo mining complex

The Industrial Area is characterized by infrastructures, such as, Copper and Zinc Process Plants, Industrial Water Tank, Heap, Contaminated Water Retention Dams, and Water Treatment Plants. Infrastructures that stand out at the IRCL are Tailings Management Facility (TMF), Paste Plant, Water Storage Dams, and Water Treatment Plants [11].

The mining operations are split between two processing plants, namely the Copper Plant and the Zinc Plant. Both plants use conventional flowsheets consisting of crushing, grinding and flotation [12]. The Copper Plant began ore processing in 1988 and has undergone numerous

stages of expansion [12]. The plant now treats copper ore through two grinding lines with separate rougher flotation and common cleaning flotation circuits. The current Zinc Plant was upgraded in 2010 and now has a zinc ore treatment design capacity of 1.1Mtpa. The ore is treated using a sequential copper/lead and zinc flowsheet [12].

The mine has distinct areas with mineral deposits and three dismantling methods are used in operations: Drift & Fill, Bench & Fill, and Mini-Bench & Fill. The dismantling method is chosen according to the morphological and typological characteristics of the mineral deposits. After dismantling, the void originated from mineral extraction is filled with backfill, to minimize surface subsidence [11]. The mine uses two main types of backfill: hydraulic sand fill and paste fill [12]. The hydraulic fill is prepared in a surface plant and consists of imported aeolian sand, cycloned tailings and cement. Paste fill contains cycloned tailings and cement and is mixed in the Paste Plant. Mined ore and development waste from operations are transferred to the processing plants, while tailings are taken to the TMF [12]. Mine water is pumped to the surface for further treatment, to be recirculated or discharge into the environment [12].

In brief, there are four liquid effluents coming from the mining complex: mine water or industrial effluent; residual water from the thickening tailings; domestic residual water; pluvial contaminated water [11].

- Mine water has origin in the existing water in the rock, hydraulic drilling, and hydraulic filling. In underground works, mine water drainage is carried out along the ramps, chimneys, and drainage holes, up to mine scroll level 700m and 550m. From there, it enters in a Water Treatment Installation to go through a flocculation-decantation process, and both water and sludge resulting from this operation are pumped separately to the surface. While the sludge is taken to the IRCL for further processing, the water is recirculated for industrial purposes or treated at the Mine Water Treatment Plant Treated water is discharged into the nearby Oeiras River [11;12].

- Residual water from the thickening tailings is taken to the Paste Plant and recirculated to the IRCL. After treatment, it is discharged into the Oeiras River or stored in the Cerro da Mina Water Storage Dam [11].

- Domestic residual water is circulated to the Residual Water Treatment Plant, and the resulting effluent is discharged into the Oeiras River. In case of emergency, the effluent is taken to the Water Contaminated Retention Dams [11].
- Pluvial contaminated water is stored in five Water Contaminated Retention Dams. The majority of the water stored in these dams is lost by evaporation, but when its level is close to the storage limit, the water is circulated to the IRCM, and then to the RCM [11].

4. What are the impacts of mining on water resources in the Castro Verde area?

In mining operations, the orebody has a high pyrite (iron sulfide) content, so waste rock and tailings have the potential to oxidize and produce acid, i.e., they have a high acid production potential [12]. Moreover, the explosives used for blasting the orebody induce the elevation in concentrations of nitrogen compounds and sulphates [13]. Within the mine premises, the groundwater is a significant aquifer and connects to local water supplies and a significant river that passes close to the mine, separating it from the TMF. Tailing's delivery and return water pipelines must cross the river [13].

High sulphates and metals due to oxidation of pyrite in the underground strata, tailings solids and waste rock are a potential threat to surface water systems through causing acidic conditions [13]. As with most mine sites, rainfall runoff is potentially contaminated with suspended solids and dissolved pollutants, including acid, which if uncontrolled could severely contaminate the Oeiras River [13].

There is a potential risk to groundwater quality due to seepage from the TMF. Monitoring of groundwater both upstream and downstream of the TMF reveals that there is a contaminated plume dispersing downstream [12]. Additionally, the pumping of water from the mine has depressed the water table over a significant area around the mine [12].

5. What are the characteristics of Mine Waters? What are the main types of Mine Water Pollution in this area? Which Mine water treatment systems are used?

Mine water from mining operations is alkaline mainly, due to the cement used in the hydraulic backfill, and contains sulphates (from oxidation of sulfides), ammonia and nitrate

from blasting. Other contaminants are elevated but do not constitute a significant environmental hazard [3]. The mine water management System is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Mine Water Management System [13].

Mine component	Inputs	Outputs
Mine (underground)	Mainly groundwater, together with water draining from the paste and hydraulic backfill, recycled water and fresh water from the Santa Clara Reservoir, used for dust suppression.	Water pumped from the mine has a high pH due to the cement used in the backfill operations. Most of the water is piped to a water treatment area (ETAM) before discharge into the Oeiras River.
Mill & process plants	A combination of: Internally recycled water from the concentrate thickeners Externally recycled industrial water, from the mine and tailings fed from the TMF Fresh make-up water, from both Santa Clara reservoir and from a tailings water purification plant	Output from the plant goes mainly to the tailings facility, or into the paste tailings backfill underground
Tailings Management Facility (TMF)	Mainly from the plant, mine sewage treatment works and pollution control dams, but also significant input from direct rainfall. Catchment dams divert rainfall from clean areas around the facility, so it does not enter the dam.	Most (60% - 70%) is recycled back to the plant, but other losses include evaporation (20% - 25%), infiltration (25%), retained water (6% - 7%) and the nano-filtration plant during high rainfall events, for discharge into the Oeiras River.
Mine surface	Rainfall onto the mine catchment is contained in pollution control dams Foul drainage from the mine facilities is treated in ETAR	Polluted water and treated effluent are pumped to the TMF

There are several water treatment facilities which ensure a high-water recycling ability and effluent treatment before discharge into the environment [13]:

- ETAM – for treating mine water, which consists of an open, U-shaped lagoon, for removal of sediment, aeration, and pH control (CO₂ injection to lower the alkalinity). Discharge is direct to the Oeiras River

- ETAP – water purification for production of potable water for the mine, from the Santa Clara reservoir
- ETAR – conventional sewage treatment plant
- Nano-Filtration plant found at the Cerro do Lobo Tailings Management Facility (TMF).

6. How important are groundwater resources for mine production processes? What is the estimated volume of water needed for the mining activities in the Castro Verde area?

The total water requirement for the mine and plant is approximately 180 m³/hr with as much as 75% of the volume being reused. Fresh water is supplied to the mine via a 400mm diameter pipeline from the Santa Clara reservoir, approximately 40km west of the mine. Supply capacity is 600 m³/hr whilst storage facilities close to the mine hold 30 days' requirements [12].

7. How does groundwater quality degradation arise from mining activity in the Castro Verde area?

Any pollution of groundwater from the mine will report to the mine sump. A Risk Assessment undertaken identified mine water seepage from the unlined pollution prevention dams as a potential risk to groundwater [12]. Whilst the walls of the TMF are lined for geotechnical stability reasons, the base is not and gradual dispersal of leachate via the base of the TMF was identified [12]. There is potential for groundwater impacts from the TMF to be migrating offsite, either via a diffuse plume or via a fracture pathway [12].

Nevertheless, according to the third cycle of the Management Plan for the Guadiana Hydrographic Region (PGRH, 2022-2027) [14], between 2016 and 2021, the groundwater in the region under study was characterized by a good chemical status (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Groundwater status classification (adapted from [14])

8. Are there any specific Mine water regulation/standards issued by the Portuguese / local authorities?

Certain groups of substances are considered dangerous due to their persistence, toxicity, or bioaccumulation. The concern about their presence in water has resulted in the adoption of several community acts, all of which have been transposed into national law. Two lists of substances are defined (Annex XIX of Decree-Law Nº 236/98), and the Portuguese Environmental Agency must [15]:

- carry out an inventory of discharges containing substances from List I
- take measures to eliminate pollution by substances included in List I and to reduce, through the implementation of specific programs, pollution by substances in List II
- establish emission standards for the discharge of substances included in Lists I and II
- define action programs for the long-term reduction of List II substances, including emission limits and quality standards for water, considering the best available technologies.

For List I substances, the European Council has defined emission standards for effluent discharges and quality standards for water resources. For substances in List II (which includes substances belonging to groups of substances in List I for which limits have not been established), each Member State of the European Union must establish the limits [15].

List I include certain individual substances differentiated primarily based on toxicity, persistence, and bioaccumulation, apart from those that are biologically harmless or that quickly turn into substances biologically harmless (Table 3) [15]:

Table 3. Substances included in List I [11].

List I
1) Organic halogen compounds and substances that can produce such compounds in the aquatic environment;
2) Organic phosphorus compounds
3) Organic tin compounds
4) Substances which have been shown to have a carcinogenic effect in or through the aquatic environment
5) Mercury and mercury compounds
6) Cadmium and cadmium compounds
7) Persistent mineral oils and persistent hydrocarbons of petroleum origin
8) Resistant synthetic materials that can float, remain suspended or sink and that can harm any use of water

List II includes substances that have a harmful effect on the aquatic environment, which may, however, be limited to a certain area and which depends on the characteristics of the receiving waters and their location (Table 4) [15].

Table 4. Substances included in List II [11]

List II
1) Metalloids and metals, as well as the respective compounds: zinc, copper nickel, chromium, lead, selenium, arsenic, antimony, molybdenum, titanium, tin, barium, beryllium, boron, uranium, vanadium, cobalt, thallium, tellurium, silver
2) Biocides and their derivatives that do not appear in list I
3) Substances which have a harmful effect on the taste or smell of products for human consumption derived from the aquatic environment, as well as compounds capable of producing such substances in water;
4) Toxic or persistent organic silicon compounds and substances which can produce such compounds in water, excluding those which are biologically harmless, or which rapidly transform into harmless substances;
5) Inorganic phosphorus and elemental phosphorus compounds
6) Non-persistent mineral oils and non-persistent hydrocarbons of petroleum origin

-
- 7) cyanides, fluorides
 - 8) Substances that exert an unfavorable influence on the oxygen balance, namely ammonia and nitrites
-

9. What are the Impacts mining activities on local groundwater drainage, flow, and discharge? In what ways do mining activities interact with groundwater systems?

The pumping of water from the mine has depressed the water table over a significant area around the mine. As the mine workings deepen, some water supply wells dried up and alternative supplies of water have been provided as appropriate to compensate for this [3].

10. What are the impacts of mining on physical hydrogeology in the Castro Verde area *(i.e. Focus on the following topics: The types of mines which exist (deep, surface), their methods of working and the geometry of voids which they produce? Mine wastes: their origins and nature. The implications of the above for physical hydrogeology of mined ground,*

Neves-Corvo has been developed as an underground operation, exploiting a number of polymetallic sulphide orebodies [12]. The orebody has a high pyrite (iron sulphide) content, so waste rock and tailings have the potential to oxidise and produce acid [12]. Mining methods have been dictated by geology and geotechnical considerations and at the present time, both drift and fill and bench and fill are utilised with the fill comprising either hydraulic fill or more recently, paste fill [12]. As output, these activities originate waste rock, tailings and wastewater that needs to be taken out from the underground. The pumping of water from the mine is depressing the water table over a significant area around the mine. It is understood that water supply wells around the mine have dried up as the mine workings deepen [12].

11. Can mine drainage operations be an important source of water-supply in the Castro Verde area?

The water from mine drainage that is treated at a Portable Water Treatment Plant, is used for human consumption at the mine and three nearby villages (Neves da Graça, Senhora da Graça de Padrões and A-do-Corvo) [12]. However, mine water is not the most important source of water supply to the villages.

12. What is being done/What measures have been put in place by Castro Verde local authorities to mitigate impacts of mining on groundwater?

There is potential for groundwater impacts from the Tailings Management Facility to be migrating offsite, either via a diffuse plume or via a fracture pathway. As a result, an Environmental Health and Safety Audit recommended the hiring of consultants to assess the existing soil and groundwater monitoring network and to propose improvements to be subsequently incorporated into the closure plan, and this work has been initiated by the Mine [12]. The Mine must also prepare annual monitoring reports to be delivered to the authorities.

Upon mine closure, the approved Environmental Impact Study [11] refers that the groundwater will rebound to its natural level when mine pumping ceases. Initially this will flush or leach any residual dissolved metals, acid, or alkalis from within the mine workings. The natural groundwater flow will be towards the Oeiras River, however no information on the extent or impacts of a post-closure plume is available at present. Further monitoring after mine closure will be needed.

13. What are the main “In situ remediation technologies” used in this basin (there may be one technology or there many/combined i.e. Permeable Reactive Barrier Systems, Wetland Systems...? Non-conventional wastewater treatment?) What is the volume of treated water?

Before discharge into the environment, the industrial effluent is treated in several facilities, such as ETAM, ETAP, ETAR and Nano-filtration (previously referred in section 5 of this survey).

The Nano-filtration plant is the most recent technology implemented at the mining complex. It consists of three sequential filtration stages: sand filters, microfiltration, and reverse osmosis. Water used for backflushing the filters is discharged back to the TMF. The plant has a capacity of 150m³/hour of treated water. This plant was required for three reasons [13]:

- To treat excess water accumulating on the TMF prior to discharge
- To substitute fresh water from the Santa Clara reservoir, the cost of which is escalating, and availability is not guaranteed

- As a treatment facility for dam seepage water after closure of the TMF.

Table 5 shows the total volume of effluent discharged into the Oeiras River after treatment and its relative volume per amount of extracted ore (m³/ton) from 2013 to 2015 [11].

Table 5. Total volume of effluent discharged into the Oeiras River between 2013 and 2015 [11]

Discharged Effluent	2013	2014	2015
Total volume after treatment	2 003 649 000	979 911 000	75 566 000
Relative volume per amount of extracted ore (m ³ /ton)	571,96	267,86	25,27

14. Are there any modelling mine water flow or geochemical processes controlling/monitoring mine water pollution?

In terms of surface water resources, SOMINCOR monitors the environment receiving the discharge, the treated effluents discharged into it, and the recirculated water from IRCL [11].

The effluent and surface water quality control program are defined in accordance with the requirements of Environmental License No. 19/2008, of 3 March, issued for the Neves-Corvo Mining Complex [11].

IRCL's recirculated water quality control program is carried out in accordance with the provisions of the respective Environmental Impact Declaration issued within the scope of the 2007 Neves-Corvo Mine Environmental Impact Study [11].

SOMINCOR has been developing, since 1991, an intense systematic analytical program to monitor the quality of water and liquid effluents, in addition to controlling the treatment processes and the quality of the water for mine supply [11]. Tables 6 and 7 show the performed monitoring program (analyzed parameters and analysis frequency) for treated industrial effluent and IRCL recirculated water, respectively.

Table 6. Monitoring program of treated industrial effluent at SOMINCOR's laboratories [11]

Parameter	Monitoring Frequency
Average Flow	Daily/continuous
Electrical Conductivity	
Dissolved Oxygen	

pH	
Temperature	
Ammoniacal Nitrogen	
Total Nitrogen	
Chlorides	
Total Copper	Biweekly
Nitrates	
Nitrites	
Sulfates	
Total Arsenic	
Cadmium	
Biochemical Oxygen Demand	
Chemical Oxygen Demand	
Total Lead	
Chromium	Monthly
Total Iron	
Total Manganese	
Mercury	
Total Nickel	
Total Suspended Solids	
Total Zinc	

It should be noted that, according to the Environmental License, the samples must be representative of the discharge in a period of 24 hours and proportional to the flow.

Table 7. Monitoring program of the recirculated water from the IRCL at SOMINCOR's laboratories [11]

Parameter	Monitoring Frequency
Chlorides	
Total Copper	
Electrical Conductivity	Biweekly
Dissolved Oxygen	
pH	
Sulfates	
Total Arsenic	
Calcium	
Biochemical Oxygen Demand	Monthly
Chemical Oxygen Demand	
Total Suspended Solids	
Total Zinc	
Nitrates	
Ammoniacal Nitrogen	Quarterly
Kjeldahl Nitrogen	

Carbonates	
Alkalinity	
Total Hardness	
Total Dissolved Solids	
Total Cadmium	
Total Lead	
Total Chromium	Annually
Total Nickel	
Total Mercury	
Total Manganese	

In addition, other periodic analyzes of the treated industrial effluent are carried out in external laboratories (Table 8).

Table 8. Monitoring program of treated industrial effluent at external laboratories [11]

Parameter	Monitoring Frequency
Aluminum	
Tin	Monthly
Phenols	
Total Phosphorus	Quartely
Sulfides	
Antimony	
Barium	
Beryllium	
Boron	
Cobalt	
Tributyl Phosphate	Annually
Molybdenum	
Silver	
Selenium	
Thallium	
Titanium	
Vanadium	

Monitoring of the environment receiving the discharge from Neves-Corvo Mining Complex is carried out in 10 sampling sites, spread over the three water lines influenced by the complex: Lajes Stream, Oeiras River and Guadiana River [11]. Qualitative analysis is performed in the laboratory owned by SOMINCOR. The monitoring program (analyzed parameters and analysis frequency) of the environment receiving mine discharge is presented in Table 9.

Table 9. Monitoring program of the environment receiving discharge from the mining complex [11]

Parameter	Monitoring Frequency
Non-ionized ammonia	Monthly
Ammoniacal Nitrogen	
Kjeldahl Nitrogen	
Biochemical Oxygen Demand	
Chemical Oxygen Demand	
Chlorides	
Soluble Copper	
Total Copper	
Conductivity	
Phosphates	
Nitrates	
Nitrites	
Dissolved Oxygen	
pH	
Total Suspended Solids	
Sulfates	
Temperature	
Total Arsenic	
Total Iron	Quarterly
Total Mercury	

Regarding the monitoring program for groundwater resources, Table 10 shows the measured parameters and corresponding frequency of measurements [17].

Table 10. Monitoring program of groundwater resources [17]

Parameters	Monitoring Frequency
pH	Quarterly
Electrical Conductivity	
Chlorides	
Calcium	
Nitrates	
Copper	
Sulfates	
Total Arsenic	
Dissolved Oxygen	Annually
Sodium	

Potassium
Total Hardness
Nitrites
Ammoniacal Nitrogen
Total Suspended Solids
Total Zinc
Total Iron
Total Manganese
Mercury
Total Lead
Polinuclear Aromatic Hydrocarbons

- 15. Are there any conducted cost benefit analyses relating to environmental impacts of mining activities, in the Castro Verde area? (e.g. wastewater management, water use, remediation and compliance costs, monitoring)**

By endorsing the concept of Sustainable Development, SOMINCOR assumed the important commitment of developing management techniques in environmental matters at a level comparable to those of technical-economic management. In this sense, being aware of its social responsibilities, SOMINCOR has been promoting an attitude of protection of the environment and natural resources, aiming to provide its contribution to improving the quality of life of the local and regional population [11;12;13;15]. However, from the available Environmental Impact Studies and Technical Reports, the cost benefit analyses only refer to an employability increase and its durability, due to mining activity. It is worth to mention that the fact SOMINCOR has been complying with government environmental laws, brings awareness about regional environmental status.

- 16. What are the impacts of mining water pollution on people living and farming activities in the Castro Verde area?**

Mine water supplied to urban infrastructures does not constitute a negative impact to people living in the region. Before being discharged into the environment, mine water goes through different treatment processes to comply with the water consumption standards stipulated by the government [11]. Nevertheless, the monitoring program implemented by SOMINCOR to monitor soil contamination identified some potential threats to farming activity. In some

agricultural areas, metals such as arsenic, mercury, copper, zinc, and lead, are characterized by concentrations higher than the admissible limit value, which in turn, affect the quality of the crops [11]. This appears to be a consequence of wind-blown from the uncovered stockpiling mining areas and conveyor transfer points [11].

17. Please provide water quality analyses (recently sampled on site) relative to groundwater and surface water?

Figure 8. Locations of stations

We use the SNIRH (National Information System of Water Resources) database to provide water quality analysis data. Although being the national information system, the available monitoring data is not regularly sampled, and in some cases, data is missing. In this section, we recur to 2 stations of the groundwater [18] and 1 station of the surface water [19] quality monitoring networks, to provide water quality analysis. The locations of the stations are shown in Figure 8.

The data from the 2 stations of the groundwater quality monitoring network is presented in Table 11. These data concern the maximum and mean values of the monitored parameters for the period between April 2015 to March 2021.

Table 11. Maximum and mean values of the monitored parameters at stations 548/25 and 572/16 of the groundwater quality monitoring network for the period between April 2015 to March 2021 [18]

Parameter	Unit	Value	Station		VMA
			548/25	572/16	
pH	Sorensen scale	Maximum	7.9	8.1	5.5 – 9.0
		Mean	7.6	7.74	
Conductivity	µs/cm at 20°C	Maximum	N/A	N/A	1000
		Mean	N/A	N/A	
Chlorides	mg/L Cl	Maximum	284	110	200
		Mean	185.5	77.39	
Calcium	mg/L Ca	Maximum	N/A	N/A	-
		Mean	N/A	N/A	
Nitrates	mg/L NO ₃	Maximum	12	2	50
		Mean	7	2	
Copper	mg/L Cu	Maximum	N/A	N/A	1.0
		Mean	N/A	N/A	
Sulphates	mg/L SO ₄	Maximum	76	150	250
		Mean	60.92	103.15	
Total Arsenic	mg/L As	Maximum	0.0044	0.0027	0.1
		Mean	0.0037	0.0013	
Dissolved Oxygen	%	Maximum	93	76	30
		Mean	69.3	56.87	
Sodium		Maximum	N/A	N/A	-
		Mean	N/A	N/A	
Potassium		Maximum	N/A	N/A	-
		Mean	N/A	N/A	
Total Hardness	mg/L CaCO ₃	Maximum	270	380	-
		Mean	270	330	
Nitrites	mg/L NO ₂	Maximum	0.03	0.03	-
		Mean	0.03	0.03	
Ammoniacal	mg/L	Maximum	0.33	0.08	4.0

Nitrogen	NH ₄	Mean	0.09	0.04	
Total Suspended Solids	mg/L	Maximum	N/A	N/A	25
		Mean	N/A	N/A	
Total Zinc	mg/L Zn	Maximum	0.05	0.15	5.0
		Mean	0.038	0.06	
Total Iron	mg/L Fe	Maximum	0.15	0.34	1.0
		Mean	0.086	0.24	
Total Manganese	mg/L Mn	Maximum	0.83	0.6	1.0
		Mean	0.43	0.37	
Mercury	mg/L Hg	Maximum	1.74E-04	5.3E-05	0.001
		Mean	4.75E-05	2.73E-05	
Total Lead	mg/L Pb	Maximum	N/A	N/A	0.05
		Mean	N/A	N/A	
Polinuclear Aromatic Hydrocarbons	µg/L	Maximum	N/A	N/A	-
		Mean	N/A	N/A	

VMA (maximum admissible value) according to annex I of decree-law n° 236/98

Table 12 shows the maximum and mean values of the monitored parameters at station 28J/02 (Oeiras River) for a period between January 2017 and December 2019.

Table 12. Maximum and mean values of the monitored parameters at station 28J/02 (Oeiras River) of the surface water quality monitoring network for the period between April 2015 to March 2021 [19]

Parameter	Unit	Value	Station 28J/02	VLE
Ammoniacal Nitrogen	mg/L NH ₄	Maximum	0.004	10
		Mean	0.003	
Kjeldahl Nitrogen	mg/L N	Maximum	1	-
		Mean	0.53	
Biochemical Oxygen Demand	mg/L O ₂	Maximum	3	40
		Mean	3	
Chemical Oxygen Demand	mg/L O ₂	Maximum	33	150
		Mean	18.7	
Chlorides	mg/L	Maximum	130	-

		Mean	72.7	
Dissolved Copper	mg/L	Maximum	0.024	1
		Mean	0.016	
Conductivity	µS/cm	Maximum	N/A	-
		Mean	N/A	
Phosphates	mg/L PO ₄	Maximum	0.063	-
		Mean	0.063	
Nitrates	mg/L NO ₃	Maximum	5.2	50
		Mean	1.03	
Nitrites	mg/L NO ₂	Maximum	0.075	5
		Mean	0.018	
Dissolved Oxygen	%	Maximum	N/A	-
		Mean	N/A	
pH	Sorensen scale	Maximum	N/A	6.0 – 9.0
		Mean	N/A	
Total Suspended Solids	mg/L	Maximum	27	60
		Mean	6.31	
Sulphates	mg/L SO ₄	Maximum	180	2000
		Mean	106.29	
Temperature	°C	Maximum	N/A	-
		Mean	N/A	
Total Arsenic	mg/L	Maximum	0.004	1
		Mean	0.003	
Total Iron	mg/L Fe	Maximum	0.61	2
		Mean	0.304	
Mercury	mg/L Hg	Maximum	3.5E-04	0.05
		Mean	1.6E-04	

VLE (emission limit value) defined in the Environmental Law n° 19/2008

2.1.1.1.1. Problem identification

The main problem in Castro Verde hydrogeological system is related to the mining activities for mainly two reasons. First, the groundwater in this area is very vulnerable to contaminants originating from these activities and infiltrating the groundwater bodies, mainly due to the presence of a large tailing infrastructure. Second, the mining operations are below the water table, impacting the current groundwater level of the system and wells in neighbor regions.

The aquifer system in Castro Verde is also exposed to the risks of contamination from the exploitation of geological resources and the developed agricultural activities in the study area. Mining-related industries are also some of the greatest roots of heavy metals pollution, which is hazardous to human health and environment.

2.1.1.1.1. Selection of main hotspots

The mining company SOMINCOR has implemented a large monitoring network of piezometers (+65 observations points) around the entire infrastructure and more than 200 observation points covering the entire hydrogeological network. Both monitoring networks provide relevant information regarding the water depth and the chemical composition of the water. Additionally, the mining company is about to complete (4Q of 2022) a full monitoring study that comprises a hydrogeological numerical model of the aquifer to assess the impact of the mining activities and propose environmental actions to restore the pre-production conditions of the aquifer.

Despite the efforts, there are some problems in collaboration and communication issues with the Castro Verde mining company. Therefore, we are still not able to identify the main hotspots in this area, especially those inside the mining area and its surroundings. We still lack of data related to water Balance at Neves-Corvo Mining Complex to be able to make an acute environmental benefits assessment. This issue hinders our research work and prevents us from completing the following steps of the selection procedure related to this deliverable..

2.1.1.4. Tympaki, Greece Case Study

2.1.1.4.1. Survey

Survey Questions

WP5 Survey to acquire preliminary information on the Nitrate & Nanoparticle's pollution

Site Name: Tympaki, Greece

1. Name and email of contact person in the project team

Name:

email:

Nanoparticles Pollution

2. What are the main activities/practices using nanoparticles in Tympaki?
3. Could you list the existing industrial activities in the study area? Could you map it please?
4. In your opinion, what is the origin of water pollution by nanoparticles (Industrial activities? Wastewater treatment plant? ...)
5. What are the impacts of nanoparticles on water resources in Tympaki basin?
6. What are the characteristics of Water polluted by nanoparticles?
7. Could you please map the pollution Hotspots?
8. What are the main types of Water pollution caused by nanoparticles in this area?
9. Which treatment systems are used for decontamination?
10. How does groundwater quality degradation arise from using nanoparticles in Tympaki?
11. Are there any specific water regulation/standards issued by the Greek local authorities regarding the use of nanoparticles?
12. In what ways do nanoparticles 'users interact with groundwater systems?
13. What measures have been put in place by Tympaki local authorities to mitigate impacts of nanoparticles on groundwater?
14. What are the main "In situ remediation technologies" used in tympaki basin?
15. Are there any modeling processes controlling/monitoring water pollution by nanoparticles?

16. Are there any conducted cost-benefit analyses relating to environmental impacts of using nanoparticles in Tympaki? (e.g. wastewater management, water use, remediation and compliance costs, monitoring)
17. What are the impacts of nanoparticles water pollution on people living and farming activities in Tympaki?
18. Is it possible to send us 10 L of each water sample from each sampling point?

Nitrate Pollution

19. According to you, what are the sources of water nitrate pollution in Tympaki?
20. How nitrate contamination affected the groundwater in Tympaki?
21. Is there contamination of surface water by nitrates?
22. If so, what is its origin according to you?
23. Could you please map the pollution Hotspots?
24. What type of crops/plants do farmers grow in Tympaki?
25. What type of fertilizer do they use most?
26. What is the nitrate concentration in the fertilizers used?
27. What is the frequency of the use of fertilizers with high nitrate concentration (in time, per crop)?
28. Do farmers of study area spread livestock manure (or liquid manure) during their agricultural activities?
29. According to you, is there an excess in livestock manure spreading?
30. How many wastewaters treatment plants (WWTP) are there in the study area?
31. What is the volume of treated water in Tympaki?
32. Where do they discharge their rejections?
33. Have you analyzed the water released by the WWTP? Do they meet the standards?
34. Is there a hydraulic connection between the water table and surface water (rivers, ..)?
35. If so, what is the type of connection? (contribution of groundwater to rivers, groundwater recharge by rivers, ..)
36. In your opinion, could the nitrate contamination be of domestic origin?
37. Is the whole urban area connected to the sanitation network?
38. If not, where is the urban wastewater discharged?

39. Are industries connected to the sanitation network?
40. If not, where do they discharge their wastewater?
41. Have you analyzed the water released by the industrial units? Do they meet the standards?
42. Is there a eutrophication problem in the study area?
43. What are the main “In situ remediation technologies” used in Tympaki basin relative to nitrate pollution?
44. Are there any conducted cost-benefit analyses relating to environmental impacts of nitrate pollution in Tympaki?
45. Could you please provide us the water quality analyses (recently sampled on site) relative to groundwater and surface water?
46. Is it possible to send us 10 L of each water sample from each sampling point?

Survey results

1. Name and email of contact person in the project team

Name: TUC TEAM

email: karatzas@mred.tuc.gr

Nanoparticles Pollution

2. What are the main activities/practices using nanoparticles in Tympaki?

Potentially from fertilizers and pesticides

3. Could you list the existing industrial activities in the study area? Could you map it please?

Limited industrial activities, small industries in food production, detergents, steel and glass, Wastewater treatment

4. In your opinion, what is the origin of water pollution by nanoparticles (Industrial activities? Wastewater treatment plant? ...)

Agricultural

5. What are the impacts of nanoparticles on water resources in Tympaki basin?

Non traceable because there is not specific sampling campaign for nanoparticles

6. What are the characteristics of Water polluted by nanoparticles?

N/A

7. Could you please map the pollution Hotspots?

N/A

8. What are the main types of Water pollution caused by nanoparticles in this area?

N/A

9. Which treatment systems are used for decontamination?

N/A

10. How does groundwater quality degradation arise from using nanoparticles in Tympaki?

No information

11. Are there any specific water regulation/standards issued by the Greek local authorities regarding the use of nanoparticles?

EU REGULATIONS

12. In what ways do nanoparticles 'users interact with groundwater systems?

Indirectly through the use of pesticides and fertilizers

13. What measures have been put in place by Tympaki local authorities to mitigate impacts of nanoparticles on groundwater?

Non

14. What are the main "In situ remediation technologies" used in tympaki basin?

Non

15. Are there any modeling processes controlling/monitoring water pollution by nanoparticles?

In lab scale only

16. Are there any conducted cost-benefit analyses relating to environmental impacts of using nanoparticles in Tympaki? (e.g. wastewater management, water use, remediation and compliance costs, monitoring)

No

17. What are the impacts of nanoparticles water pollution on people living and farming activities in Tympaki?

N/A

18. Is it possible to send us 10 L of each water sample from each sampling point?

There is no ongoing grab sampling campaign by the authorities

Nitrate Pollution

19. According to you, what are the sources of water nitrate pollution in Tympaki?

Fertilizers

20. How nitrate contamination affected the groundwater in Tympaki?

Periodical high concentrations

21. Is there contamination of surface water by nitrates?

NO

22. If so, what is its origin according to you?

NA

23. Could you please map the pollution Hotspots?

Farmhouses

24. What type of crops/plants do farmers grow in Tympaki?

Vegetables, vineyards, olive trees

25. What type of fertilizer do they use most?

Ammonia, nitrates, nitrogen, Calcium, Phosphates, Potassium, Magnesium, organic

26. What is the nitrate concentration in the fertilizers used?

20%

27. What is the frequency of the use of fertilizers with high nitrate concentration (in time, per crop)?

4 periods/year minimum

28. Do farmers of study area spread livestock manure (or liquid manure) during their agricultural activities?

Yes

29. According to you, is there an excess in livestock manure spreading?

No

30. How many wastewaters treatment plants (WWTP) are there in the study area?

One

31. What is the volume of treated water in Tympaki?

3000 m³/day

32. Where do they discharge their rejections?

Sea

33. Have you analyzed the water released by the WWTP? Do they meet the standards?

Regional government of Crete do and they comply with the standards

34. Is there a hydraulic connection between the water table and surface water (rivers, ..)?

Yes

35. If so, what is the type of connection? (contribution of groundwater to rivers, groundwater recharge by rivers, ..)

Groundwater recharge by rivers

36. In your opinion, could the nitrate contamination be of domestic origin?

Yes

37. Is the whole urban area connected to the sanitation network?

Yes

38. If not, where is the urban wastewater discharged?

NA

39. Are industries connected to the sanitation network?

Yes

40. If not, where do they discharge their wastewater?

NA

41. Have you analyzed the water released by the industrial units? Do they meet the standards?

Regional government of Crete do and they comply with the standards

42. Is there a eutrophication problem in the study area?

Rare

43. What are the main “In situ remediation technologies” used in Tympaki basin relative to nitrate pollution?

Non

44. Are there any conducted cost-benefit analyses relating to environmental impacts of nitrate pollution in Tympaki?

Non

45. Could you please provide us the water quality analyses (recently sampled on site) relative to groundwater and surface water?

Yes we will try

46. Is it possible to send us 10 L of each water sample from each sampling point?

There is no ongoing grab sampling campaign by the authorities

2.1.1.4.2. Problem identification

The Tympaki basin is under the continuous pressure of overexploitation of groundwater resources. Until 2012 when a reservoir of 17Mm³ capacity was built the only water resource for all the activities (agricultural and human needs) was the Tympaki aquifer. Since 2015 all the wells in the area have been registered and a balanced surface water and groundwater use is applied to cover the needs. There are about 400 pumping wells in the area (public and private) with permit to exploit groundwater. Regional government of Crete monitors and controls pumping quantity in annual scale and applies restrictions measures. The result of the constant overexploitation of the aquifer is saltwater intrusion at the coastal part of the basin. Nitrate pollution occurs locally and periodically in the area as a result of the use of fertilizers.

2.1.1.4.3. Selection of main hotspots

The great number of farm houses and the intensive agricultural activity in the Tympaki basin are responsible for environmental stresses in the area. The focus of this project is on the control of overexploitation of the aquifer providing a balanced surface water groundwater use. In addition, the focus is on the study of the salt water intrusion front depending on the exploitation of the aquifer. The spatial distribution of Cl⁻ concentrations in the area will be studied using numerical modeling. The electrical conductivity in groundwater will be studied as well using geophysical data. Nitrate pollution has been observed at local scale closely to clusters of farmhouses and will be further explored in association with land reclamation organizations that monitor regularly hotspot areas.

2.1.1.5. Konya, Turkey Case Study

2.1.1.5.1. Survey

[Survey Questions](#)

WP5 / Survey to acquire preliminary information on the Nitrate & Salinity pollution

Site Name: Konya, Turkey

1. Name and email of contact person in the project team

Name:

email:

2. According to you, what are the sources of water nitrate pollution in Konya?
3. How nitrate contamination affected the groundwater in Konya?
4. Is there contamination of surface water by nitrates?
5. If so, what is its origin according to you?
6. Could you please map the nitrate pollution hotspots?
7. According to you, what are the sources of water salinity pollution in Konya?
8. How the salinity affected the groundwater in Konya?
9. What is its origin according to you?
10. Could you please map the salinity pollution hotspots?
11. What type of crops/plants do farmers grow in Konya?
12. What type of fertilizer do they use most?
13. What is the nitrate concentration in the fertilizers used?
14. What is the frequency of the use of fertilizers with high nitrate concentration (in time, per crop)?
15. Do farmers of study area spread livestock manure(or liquid manure) during their agricultural activities?
16. According to you, is there an excess in livestock manure spreading?
17. How many wastewaters treatment plants (WWTP) are there in the study area?
18. What is the volume of treated water in Konya?
19. Where do they discharge their rejections?
20. Have you analyzed the water released by the WWTP? Do they meet the standards?
21. Is there a hydraulic connection between the water table and surface water (rivers, ..)?
22. If so, what is the type of connection? (Contribution of groundwater to rivers, groundwater recharge by rivers, ..)
23. In your opinion, could the nitrate contamination be of domestic origin?
24. Is the whole urban area connected to the sanitation network?

25. If not, where is the urban wastewater discharged?
26. Are industries connected to the sanitation network?
27. If not, where do they discharge their wastewater?
28. Could you list the existing industrial activities in the study area? Could you map it please?
29. Have you analyzed the water released by the industrial units? Do they meet the standards?
30. Is there a eutrophication problem in the study area?
31. What are the main “In situ remediation technologies” used in Konya basin relative to nitrate & salinity pollution?
32. Are there any conducted cost-benefit analyses relating to environmental impacts of nitrate pollution in Konya?
33. Could you please provide us the water quality analyses (recently sampled on site) relative to groundwater and surface water?
34. Is it possible to send us 10 L of each water sample from each sampling point?

Survey results

Site Name: Konya, Turkey

1. Name and email of contact person in the project team

Name: İzel Uygur

email: izel.uygur@boun.edu.tr

2. According to you, what are the sources of water nitrate pollution in Konya?

Based on the available data, there does not seem to be a severe nitrate contamination in the basin. However, potential sources are as follows: agricultural non-point sources due to heavy fertilizer use, domestic waste [20].

3. How nitrate contamination affected the groundwater in Konya?

The basin has a very large area, therefore, salinity and nitrate concentrations vary between different regions. Bozdağ's study [21] shows that in Çumra region (southern part of the basin), nitrate concentrations in 49 samples are in between 0,18 - 7,33 mg/L and samples

were found suitable for irrigation purposes. Conversely, another study by Büyük et al. [20] studies Karapınar region, which is spatially close to Çumra. The nitrate concentration in their 19 samples range between 3,4 - 18,9 mg/L, which is significantly higher than the samples in Bozdağ's study. Büyük et al. conclude that the nitrate pollution in Karapınar is due to anthropogenic activities and is related to high levels of N-fertilizer use following groundwater irrigation.

4. Is there contamination of surface water by nitrates?

We do not have data on surface water quality data. Tuz Lake located north of the Konya Basin receives treated wastewater discharge and may have some nitrate pollution.

5. If so, what is its origin according to you?

According to Diri's study [22] nitrate concentration observed in samples from the surface water bodies over the basin is not threatening. 17 surface water samples taken in 2014 have nitrate concentrations varying between 0.20 - 4.10 mg/L. It should be noted that the study covers the period 2006-2014, and the highest observed nitrate concentration was in 2007 and above 10 mg/L.

6. Could you please map the nitrate pollution hotspots?

It is hard to map it since it has been caused mostly by non-point sources.

7. According to you, what are the sources of water salinity pollution in Konya?

Dissolution of minerals from Soil and geological structures, Salt Lake, excess reliance on groundwater for irrigation along with high levels of evaporation, inadequate drainage of excess water (local stakeholders indicate that this problem has been somewhat addressed in recent years) and cultivation practices can all be sources of salinity pollution.

8. How the salinity affected the groundwater in Konya?

Revisiting Bozdağ [21] and Büyük et al. [20] studies, while the EC values in Çumra ranges from 582 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 6240 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, EC around Karapınar is in between 270 - 4300 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. Currently, our understanding is that salination is not an immediate problem in the basin; decreasing

water levels is more prioritized. However, in the future groundwater is expected to become more saline and unsuitable for irrigation, which would have both environmental and economic impacts. Surface water resources are scarce in the basin, therefore irrigated agriculture is highly dependent on availability of groundwater.

9. What is its origin according to you?

The plain has alluvial soil that is characteristically susceptible to insufficient drainage and salinity [23]. Additionally, Salt Lake in the northern part of the basin is the second most saline lake in the world and is an important salt reserve. Büyük et al. [20] identifies a natural salination cycle given that Konya is a closed basin.

10. Could you please map the salinity pollution hotspots?

We do not have sufficient data to map salinity hotspots.

11. What type of crops/plants do farmers grow in Konya?

A variety of crops are cultivated in the basin. The most popular crops are as follows: wheat, barley, maize, sugar beet, sunflower, legumes (chickpea, lentil, pea, beans), potato and so on.

12. What type of fertilizer do they use most?

There is no numerical data on fertilizer use, we only have anecdotal data from our field studies. Farmers use both chemical (synthetic) fertilizers and livestock manure as fertilizer. The use of livestock manure has been spreading lately; farmers are trying to increase the organic matter in the soil with manure. Before that, the dominant type of fertilizer was synthetic fertilizers with high nitrate concentrations. Farmers still use such synthetic fertilizers, but with the use of manure, it might be less than before.

13. What is the nitrate concentration in the fertilizers used?

We do not know all types of fertilizers that the farmers use, however below are some examples:

- DAP (diammonium phosphate) - 18% N, 46% P
- Urea - 46% N

- 20-20-20 fertilizer - 20% N (5.2% NO₃)
- MAP (monoammonium phosphate) - 12% N

14. What is the frequency of the use of fertilizers with high nitrate concentration (in time, per crop)?

To continue with the examples from the previous question, to quote a local agricultural engineer/farmer, farmers use 40 kg of DAP, 40 kg of urea, 4 kg of 20-20-20 fertilizer, 6 kg of MAP and 2 kg of potassium for maize, per decare (1000 m²) per season. We do not know the intraseasonal application frequency of those amounts.

15. Do farmers of study area spread livestock manure (or liquid manure) during their agricultural activities?

Many farmers in the region are also stock breeders. In the field trips, we found out that up to a couple of years ago, farmers were willing to pay to remove animal manure from their fields. Recently, farmers started using the manure from their animals as fertilizers in their own fields, both to cut synthetic fertilizer costs which has become very expensive over the past few years, and to increase the organic content of the soil.

16. According to you, is there an excess in livestock manure spreading?

There is no numerical data on fertilizer or manure use in agriculture. However, it is our understanding that most farmers tend to overuse fertilizers, be it chemical or livestock manure (if available to them).

17. How many wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) are there in the study area?

Please see below.

18. What is the volume of treated water in Konya?

There are 17 active and 2 non-operating wastewater treatment plants under municipalities located within the Konya Closed Basin [23]. Namely;

- Konya Metropolitan Municipality KOSKİ Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Başarakavak Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant

- Tepeköy Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Akören Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Güneysınır Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Ereğli Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Niğde Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Bor Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Çukurkuyu Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Şereflikoçhisar Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Kulu Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Aksaray Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Zincirlikuyu Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Derinkuyu Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Ulukışla Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Sultanhanı Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Altınekin Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant
- Doğanbey Wastewater Treatment Plant (inactive)
- Beyşehir Municipality Wastewater Treatment Plant (inactive)

The most recent data available is of 2020 and provided by Turkish Statistical Institute [24, 25]. According to that data there are 68 wastewater treatment plants within the administrative region of the cities that enclose the basin, namely; Konya, Aksaray, Niğde, and Karaman. These include the municipality WWTPs as well as private ones owned by industries. The total volume of water treated in those 68 plants was 111.351.000 m³ in 2020. However, since the boundaries of the basin do not overlap with the administrative units, we do not know for sure how many of the 68 facilities are located within the basin.

Table 13. Turkish Statistical Institute data from 2020 [24, 25]

	Aksaray-68	Karaman-70	Konya-42	Niğde-51	TOTAL
Number of Wastewater Treatment Plants	8	9	42	9	68
Wastewater Treatment Capacity (1000 Cubic Meters per Year)	6021	17488	107016	25316	155841
Volume of Treated Wastewater (1000 Cubic Meters per Year)	1725	6937	91341	11348	111351

19. Where do they discharge their rejections?

The largest WWTP in the basin which treats wastewater from the city of Konya discharges its wastewater in open channels to Salt Lake (Tuz Lake). No solid information about the discharge of the other WWTPs is present in the literature.

20. Have you analyzed the water released by the WWTP? Do they meet the standards?

Kurtkulak [26] analysed a pilot WWTP effluent from the region and found that the EC value ranged between 970 – 1980 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. According to the standards, $<700 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ is high quality water, and $>3000 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ is poor quality. The effluent analysed is medium quality according to the standards. Her study lacks a direct measurement of the Total Nitrogen in the treated water, but the BOD is measured as follows: the average BOD level of the influent was measured as 17.18 mg/L in 16 samples, ranging from 12 to 23 mg/L. 5 samples from the effluent was taken and the average BOD was 3.8 mg/L, ranging between 2 – 7 mg/L.

A related presentation by Aydın and Koyuncu [27] shows that for Konya WWTP, the TN level was 76 mg/L for the influent and 51 mg/L for the effluent.

21. Is there a hydraulic connection between the water table and surface water (rivers, ..)?

The streams/rivers collect surface runoff in the winter/spring months. Water in streams feed small lakes, evaporate, or feed the groundwater. The groundwater level is generally deeper, so it can be assumed that the groundwater does not feed the surface water bodies.

22. If so, what is the type of connection? (Contribution of groundwater to rivers, groundwater recharge by rivers, ..)

The connection is through recharge of groundwater by rivers and lakes. In the centre of the basin, the groundwater table is very deep.

23. In your opinion, could the nitrate contamination be of domestic origin?

According to the TÜBİTAK MAM study in 2010 [23], 96% of nitrogen pollution load was from nonpoint sources, therefore it can be interpreted that the main contributor of nitrate pollution is agricultural activities. Domestic wastes could be contributors but given that the

majority of the population is connected to the sanitation network, the major N-pollutant is the agriculture sector.

24. Is the whole urban area connected to the sanitation network?

Yes

25. If not, where is the urban wastewater discharged?

According to 2009 data, 79% of the basin population was connected to the sewer system [23]. Currently, 96% of the population is connected to the sewer system. The remaining 4% is mostly small village neighbourhoods and they still use cesspools instead. The water collected in the sewer is treated if the area is connected to a wastewater treatment plant and discharged to a receiving environment. The same data from 2009 shows that 68% of the population's wastewater was treated, while the remaining 11% was directly discharged, and the remaining 21% is not connected to the system, as mentioned above.

26. Are industries connected to the sanitation network?

27. If not, where do they discharge their wastewater?

Some organized industrial zones have their own wastewater treatment plants [23]. Others either discharge their wastewater to various streams through open channels, are connected to sewer systems where their wastewater is mixed with municipal wastewater, let rest their wastewater in mud ponds and discharge to open channels, or discharge to State Hydraulic Works' (DSİ) discharge channels.

Facilities that are not located in an organized industrial zone also have various methods [23]. Many facilities have their own wastewater treatment plants. After the treatment, water is discharged to nearby surface water bodies or streams, facility's own grounds, DSİ (State Water Works) channels, or it is used as irrigation water. Others collect wastewater and transfer the water with sewage trucks to a nearby treatment facility, where the water is discharged to the municipal sewer network after the treatment.

28. Could you list the existing industrial activities in the study area? Could you map it please?

Given that the basin has a considerably large area which does not overlap administrative borders, we can only provide information on the prominent sectors within the region. Konya Plains Project Regional Development Administration (KOP) publishes a yearly report on socio-economic indicators. According to the 2021 report [28], the following industrial activities are carried out in the region:

- Mining: 33 different minerals are found in the region. Turkey's largest aluminium and magnesite resources lie in the region, and the only aluminium factory is in Konya.
- Energy: Renewable energy investments are prominent in the region. 55% of the energy supply is from renewable resources; of those, 49,1% is solar, 34,7% is hydroelectric, the remaining is mostly wind and biogas.
- Food industry is important, given that agriculture constitutes nearly 20% of gross revenue in the region. Sugar refineries and packaged food production is prominent.
- Machine and equipment production, especially in Konya city, has nearly equal number of businesses as food production [29].

There exist 24 organized industrial zones and 57 small industrial areas in the KOP region. Once again, it should be noted that the KOP region doesn't fully overlap with the basin borders, however, it is safe to assume that most of the facilities are located in the basin.

29. Have you analysed the water released by the industrial units? Do they meet the standards?

No. The scope of our work package does not include water quality and the literature does not have specific studies focusing on water quality from industrial sites.

30. Is there a eutrophication problem in the study area?

Eutrophication is not a prominent issue in the basin. Figure 9 below shows the results of a recent study, sampling 39 streams from the basin and comparing water quality based on 9 different indices (Figure 9).

	TIT	TI	EPI-D	IPS	TDI	DSIAR	DEQI	TWQI	DDI
S01	2.31	0.83	1.02	4.15	33.1	47.7	0.00	0.00	9.32
S02	1.04	1.67	1.07	3.64	28.4	50.5	1.79	2.59	9.29
S03	2.41	2.92	1.77	2.68	48.4	42.1	2.39	2.75	9.14
S04	2.72	1.94	1.00	2.62	66.7	44.3	4.27	3.87	8.77
S05	1.74	2.56	1.14	2.91	36.3	43.4	1.90	2.51	9.30
S06	2.24	2.55	1.48	2.60	60.6	47.1	3.02	2.60	9.30
S07	1.89	2.37	1.23	3.47	44.4	51.7	2.84	2.55	9.14
S08	1.86	2.51	0.70	3.60	25.0	57.0	2.89	2.50	9.39
S09	2.13	1.59	1.42	3.54	24.1	58.1	5.00	nd	9.20
S10	1.46	1.58	0.91	3.28	35.7	58.5	3.48	2.50	9.32
S11	2.38	2.05	1.41	4.21	45.3	51.3	1.24	2.50	9.28
S12	1.94	2.23	1.05	3.54	38.8	47.3	2.39	2.58	9.21
S13	2.50	1.85	1.48	4.00	56.1	52.5	2.27	2.50	9.31
S14	2.36	1.46	1.16	3.55	28.1	58.5	nd	3.10	9.24
S15	2.10	2.15	0.99	3.44	44.7	47.3	2.71	2.86	9.24
S16	1.50	1.46	0.82	4.07	24.3	52.8	1.58	2.50	9.41
S17	2.31	1.98	1.36	3.27	38.2	51.2	3.12	2.63	9.10
S18	2.38	2.81	1.56	2.83	47.1	50.5	2.11	3.11	9.05
S19	2.27	2.41	1.57	3.00	35.0	43.4	2.12	2.00	9.09
S20	1.24	0.87	0.86	4.17	24.2	57.8	1.00	2.50	9.40
S21	2.42	2.76	1.36	1.93	32.1	42.1	2.33	2.54	9.33
S22	2.30	1.95	1.20	3.52	46.3	31.2	3.56	2.50	9.19
S23	2.51	2.43	1.23	2.08	31.6	53.3	3.28	2.50	9.27
S24	1.31	1.97	1.01	4.07	35.2	45.9	1.41	2.51	9.35
S25	1.46	1.91	0.96	3.72	35.2	50.5	1.54	2.52	9.18
S26	2.48	2.67	1.72	3.07	64.2	46.9	3.72	2.93	9.08
S27	1.41	0.99	1.07	4.04	30.9	52.5	1.68	2.54	9.33
S28	1.07	1.65	0.75	3.30	21.7	57.2	2.73	2.50	9.47
S29	1.49	1.11	1.18	4.56	28.6	29.3	1.13	1.66	9.40
S30	1.35	2.27	1.09	2.50	15.7	57.1	2.30	3.25	9.32
S31	2.34	2.75	1.63	2.41	66.2	46.0	2.73	2.54	9.08
S32	3.39	2.81	1.77	2.42	53.6	49.2	2.44	3.95	9.04
S33	1.23	2.85	1.04	1.21	29.0	62.7	2.93	2.50	9.10
S34	2.58	1.81	1.12	3.22	33.0	51.8	2.76	2.50	9.27
S35	2.52	2.63	1.42	3.13	44.8	44.8	2.27	2.71	9.11

Figure 9. Sample analysis from 39 different streams in the basin [30]

Different ecoregional diatom indices'scores of the sampling stations : Trophic index Turkey (TIT), Trophic Index (TI), Eutrophication and/or Pollution Index-Diatom (EPI-D), Trophic Diatom Index for Lakes (TDIL), Trophic Water Quality Index (TWQI), Diatom Ecological Quality Index (DEQI), Duero Diatom Index (DDI), Pollution Sensitivity Index (IPS), Trophic Diatom Index (TDI), and Diatom Species Index Australian Rivers (DSIAR).

The meaning of different colors used in the table is as follows: blue-high quality, green-good quality, yellow-moderate quality, orange-poor quality, red-bad quality nd-not detected scores.

31. What are the main “In situ remediation technologies” used in Konya basin relative to nitrate & salinity pollution?

Both Konya Closed Basin Management Plan [31] and Konya Closed Basin Protection Action Plan focus on preventive measures in terms of water quality, but neither document mention in situ remediation measures. It is understandable given that the major issue in Konya Closed Basin is currently not the water quality but decreasing water quantity. The salinity and nitrate pollution are not yet at alarming levels.

32. Are there any conducted cost-benefit analyses relating to environmental impacts of nitrate pollution in Konya?

Unfortunately, no

33. Could you please provide us the water quality analyses (recently sampled on site) relative to groundwater and surface water?

We do not have access to such analyses.

34. Is it possible to send us 10 L of each water sample from each sampling point?

We do not have access to sampling points.

2.1.1.5.2. Problem identification

The main groundwater issue in Konya Closed Basin is the water scarcity. General Directorate of State Hydraulic Works (DSİ) reports a 28m average decline in groundwater levels from 1980 to 2010s. In an inventory study carried out by DSİ 4. District Office in 2007, 94.000 groundwater wells have been identified in the basin, of which 66.808 were drilled illegally. Chamber of Geological Engineers (JMO) estimates that the groundwater sources will be available to use only for another 20-30 years given the current state of the aquifers [29]. WWF [29] also argues that the extraction rate is not linear, it rather has an increasing pattern. Overexploitation of the groundwater causes a yearly average of as high as 3 m decrease in the water table in some areas [30]. Secondary issues in the basin are salinity and pesticides.

2.1.1.5.3. Selection of main hotspots

One cannot identify specific hotspots in Konya because pollution is due to nonpoint sources. Salinity is mainly caused by the hydrogeological formation. The area surrounding the Salt Lake may be considered a salinity hotspot. Since agriculture is the most prominent sector in the region, pesticide use is common.

2.2. Procedure for capacity building

2.2.1. Local stakeholders mapping

The first step in this process is water users mapping that will direct the recognizable proof of the main local polluter/user candidate (MLPC), which happens in the accompanying step.

The MLPC is a stakeholder that adversely influences straightforwardly or indirectly the water assets. The candidates will be welcome to partake in a particular support program to improve their ability to more readily deal with the water assets concerning the sustainability objectives. The project partners will plan the support program according to the MLPC activities.

Table 14. Main local polluter/userlist, Grombalia Case study

Sector	User	Activity	Receiving environment	Main water pollution
Grombalia - Tunisia				
Industry	ARALCO	Production of food flavour		
	SIPAC	Production of Food additives)	Sanitation & Natural Network (Wadi Tahouna)	High P level ; High concentration of BOD & COD
	SNBG	Soft drinks		
	BlachisseriecentraleHôtelière	Laundry		
	Coccinelle	Laundry		

SPIM	Metal industry		
Establishment LatrousDriss	Wine production		
GTS	Jeans washing		
SONOBRA	Production of distilled alcoholic beverages		
SCAPCB	Processing and preservation of tomatoes		
Eschams	Brick sheet production	Natural Network	
TMM	Tanning		
Mazraa	Processing and preservation of poultry meat		No Data
SOTIPAPIER	Paper industry	Natural Network (Wadi Tahouna)	High salinity, High P and N level
YAB	Dairy plant	Wastewater reused in crop irrigation	

Table 15. Main local user list, Requena-Utiel Case study

Sector	User	Activity	Receiving environment	Main water pollution
Requena-Utiel - Spain				
	Irrigation Communities, predominantly S.A.T. Riegos Casas-Corrales and C.R.Riegos LasCuevas de	Agriculture		Nitrates

Utiel(see table 18 of the D5.1 [34])

Vegalfaro, Vereda Real, Coviñas, Iranzo

Winery

Nitrates

ChavezFernandez, S.L., El Terrerazo S.L., Integraciones AvicolasValencianas, S.A., Sivimar, S.L. and Integración Monteros, S.L.

Poultry and pig company

Nitrates and phosphorus

San Benedetto

Water bottling company

No data

Corporación De Rentas, S.A.

Preparation, tanning and finishing of leather

High P level; High concentration of BOD & COD

Laureano Sanchez Requena Lauria, S.L.

Poultry slaughterhouse

High concentration of BOD & COD

Although the listed users have activities that could contaminate the aquifer with the components described, no concentrations have been detected that would require classifying the aquifer as in poor chemical condition.

Table 16. Main local user list, Tympaki Case study

Sector	User	Activity	Receiving environment	Main water pollution
Tympaki - Greece				
Agricultural	Farmhouses Associations	Agricultural	Groundwater/surface water	Chlorides, Nitrates
	Open agriculture	Agricultural		
	Organizations of water management and land	Agricultural		

reclamation

MUNICIPAL
IRRIGATION AND SEWERAGE
ENTERPRISE Water
distribution

Table 17. Main local user list, Konya Case study

Sector	User	Activity	Receiving environment	Main water pollution
Konya - Turkey				
Agriculture	Farmers	Irrigation	Soil	Salinity, Nitrate
Industry		Mining		
		Energy	No specific information available :	
		Food Industry	WWTPs, Municipal sewersystem, surface water bodies-Stream	No Data
		Machine & Equipment Production		
	EtiAluminum	Aluminum Products	Own WWTP	

2.2.2. Selection procedure

The selection of the candidates that will be engaged with the instructional meeting (training session) is based on the following steps:

1. Define a shortlist from the MLPC map (with a mosaic of representativeness) according to the contamination level of waste water as well as the amount of utilization;
2. Interview with MLPC shortlist to assess their awareness about pollution and their engagement to participate in the training session (Table 18)

3. Select the most engaged candidates who experiences a high level of awareness (representatives of different sectors) (Table 19)

Table 18. User’s engagement assessment

Contacting method: via email, phone and meeting

Users	Engagement in the project
Grombalia – Tunisia	
ARALCO	not at all engaged
SIPAC	not at all engaged
SNBG	not at all engaged
BlachisseriecentraleHôtelière	not at all engaged
Coccinelle	not at all engaged
SPIM	not at all engaged
Establishment LatrousDriss	not at all engaged
GTS	Engaged, High level of awareness
SOTUFRA	not at all engaged
GIF	not at all engaged
SONOBRA	not at all engaged
SCAPCB	not at all engaged
Eschams	hesitated
TMM	Engaged, High level of awareness
Mazraa	not at all engaged
SOTIPAPIER	not at all engaged
YAB	Engaged, High level of awareness
Requena-Utiel - Spain	
IC Riegos Casas-Corrales	Not at all engaged
IC Riegos Las Cuevas de Utiel	Engaged with high level of awareness
Other IC (see table 18 of the D5.1 [34])	Some of them engaged with high level of awareness
Iranzo	Hesitant

Vegalfaro	Not at all engaged
Vereda Real	Not at all engaged
Coviñas	Not at all engaged
Chavez Fernandez, S.L.	Not at all engaged
El Terrerazo S.L.	Not at all engaged
Integraciones Avícolas Valencianas S.A.	Not at all engaged
Sivimar, S.L.	Not at all engaged
Integración Monteros, S.L.	Not at all engaged
San Benedetto	Hesitant
Corporación De Rentas, S.A.	Not at all engaged
Laureano Sanchez Requena Lauria, S.L.	Not at all engaged
Requena City Council	Engaged with high level of awareness
Tympaki, Greece	
Farmhouses Associations	engaged
Farmers Associations	engaged
Organizations of water management and land reclamation	engaged
MUNICIPAL IRRIGATION AND SEWERAGE ENTERPRISE	engaged
Region of Crete/Administration of Environment	engaged
Decentralized Administration of Crete/ Water resources directorate	engaged
Municipality of Phaistos	engaged
Hellenic Geological & Mining Research Authority	engaged
Konya, Turkey	
Farmers	Engaged, high level of interest in the project
Mining	Not engaged
Energy	Not engaged
Food Sector	Not engaged
Machine & Equipment Production	Not engaged
Eti Aluminum	Not engaged

Table 19. Selected candidates

Candidate	Sector	Activity	Main water pollution	Receiving environment
Grombalia, Tunisia				
GTS	industry	Jeans washing/ Textile	High P level, High concentration of BOD and COD	Sanitation and Natural Network
TMM		Tanning/ leather		Natural Network
YAB		Dairy plant	High salinity, High P and N levels	Wastewater reused in crop irrigation
Tympaki, Greece				
Farmers Associations	Agricultural	Agricultural	Chlorides, Nitrates	Surface water/groundwater
Organizations of water management and land reclamation	Agricultural	Water distribution	Chlorides, Nitrates	Surface water/groundwater
Konya, Turkey				
Farmers	Agriculture	Irrigation	Salinity, Nitrate	Soil
Candidate	Sector	Activity	Main problem	
Requena-Utiel - Spain				
IC Riegos Las Cuevas de Utiel	Agriculture	Vine irrigation	Aquifer overexploitation	
IC Riegos de los Ruices	Agriculture	Vine irrigation		
IC Campo Arcís	Agriculture	Vine irrigation		
IC la Vega de San Antonio	Agriculture	Vine irrigation		
IC Caudete	Agriculture	Vine and woody trees irrigation		
San Benedetto	Industry	Water bottling company		

Iranzo	Industry	Vine irrigation and wine production
Requena City Council	Urban	Urban water supply
Utiel City Council	Urban	Urban water supply

Once the candidates have been selected, the project partners’ teams ought to lead a diagnostic to comprehend the wellspring of contamination to have the option to propose a tailored solution.

For this purpose, quantitative and qualitative data should be collected.

After performing the diagnosis, the selected MLPC ought to profit from a training session by project partners’ teams. The solutions that will be proposed to the MLCP are depending on the consequences of the diagnosis.

The design of the specific training session should be based on the 4R principle (Reduce, Recycle, Reuse, and Recover).

3. References

- [1] Slama, T., Sebei, A., 2020. Spatial and temporal analysis of shallow groundwater quality using GIS, Grombalia aquifer, Northern Tunisia. *Journal of African Earth Sciences* 170 (2020) 10391
- [2] Charfi, S., Zouari, K, Feki, S., Mami, M., 2013. Study of variation in groundwater quality in a coastal aquifer in north-eastern Tunisia using multivariate factor analysis. *Quaternary International* 302 (2013) 199e209
- [3] World Health Organization (WHO)., 2017. *Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality. Incorporating First Addendum, Fourth ed.*, ISBN: 978-92-4-154995-0. https://www.who.int/water_sanitation_health/publications/drinking-water-qualityguidelines-4-including-1st-addendum/en/ [Last access 13.12.2020]
- [4] Lachaal, F., Chekirbane, A., Chargui, S., Sellami, H., Tsujimura, M., Hezzi, H., Faycel, J., Mlayah, A., 2016. Water resources management strategies and its implications on hydrodynamic and hydrochemical changes of costal groundwater: Case of Grombalia shallow aquifer, NE Tunisia, *Journal of African Earth Sciences* , doi: 10.1016/j.jafrearsci.2016.09.024
- [5] Spain. Real Decreto 1514/2009, de 2 de octubre, por el que se regula la protección de las aguas subterráneas contra la contaminación y el deterioro, núm. 255, pp. 88201 a 88215. Retrieved from <https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2009-16772>
- [6] CHJ (2015). *Plan Hidrológico de la Demarcación Hidrográfica del Júcar. Ciclo de planificación hidrológica 2015-2021*. Valencia. Retrieved from <https://www.chj.es/es-es/medioambiente/planificacionhidrologica/Paginas/PHC-2015-2021-Plan-Hidrologico-cuenca.aspx>
- [7] CHJ-IGME (2011). *Informe sobre la caracterización básica de las masas de aguas subterránea de la Confederación hidrográfica del Júcar*. Retrieved from:

- https://www.chj.es/es-es/medioambiente/planificacionhidrologica/Documents/Plan-Hidrologico-cuenca-2021-2027/Documentos iniciales/Referencia%20bibliografica/IGMEDGA,2011 MEMORIA y FICHAS_car_basica_jucar.pdf
- [8] Pablo Martínez Gil (2019). Estudio de la conexión río-acuífero del río Magro (Valencia). (Degree Final Thesis). Universitat Politècnica de València.
- [9] CHJ (2016). Plan de explotación de la masa de agua subterránea Requena-Utiel. Valencia Retrieved from:
https://www.chj.es/eses/medioambiente/PlanExplotacion/Documents/PlanExplotacion_RequenaUtiel_33_web.pdf
- [10] CHJ (2020). Plan de explotación de la masa de agua subterránea Requena-Utiel. Valencia Retrieved from:
https://www.chj.es/eses/medioambiente/PlanExplotacion/Documents/Plan_explotaci%C3%B3n_Requena-Utiel.pdf
- [11] PROCESL, 2016. SOMINCOR, Sociedade Mineira de Neves-Corvo, S.A., Projeto de Expansão do Zinco, Incluindo o Estudo de Viabilidade da Exploração do Jazigo do Lombador Fase 2 e da Expansão da Lavaria do Zinco e o Estudo de Pré-viabilidade da Expansão da Instalação de Rejeitados do Cerro do Lobo, Estudo de Impacte Ambiental, Relatório Síntese. Retrieved from:
https://siaia.apambiente.pt/AIADOC/AIA2947/eia2947_relatoriosintese20172159550.pdf
- [12] Lundin Mining, 2017. NI 43-101 Technical Report for the Neves-Corvo Mine, Portugal. Retrieved from:
<https://lundinmining.com/operations/neves-corvo/>
- [13] Lundin Mining, 2013. Technical Report for Neves-Corvo Mine and Semblana Deposit, Portugal. Retrieved from:
https://www.miningdataonline.com/reports/Neves-Corvo_2013_TR.pdf

- [14] APA, 2019. Plano de Gestão da Região Hidrográfica Guadiana (RH7), 3º Ciclo, 2022 – 2027, Questões Significativas da Água (QSiGA). Retrieved from:
https://apambiente.pt/sites/default/files/Agua/DRH/ParticipacaoPublica/PGRH/2022-2027/2_Fase/PGRH_3_RH7_QSiGA.pdf
- [15] PROCESL, 2007. Estudo de Impacte Ambiental da Mina de Neves Corvo – 2007, Relatório Final. Retrieved from:
<https://siaia.apambiente.pt/AIADOC/AIA1714/eia1714201641311711.pdf>
- [16] PROCESL, 2017. SOMINCOR – Sociedade Mineira de Neves-Corvo, S.A., Projeto de Execução da Expansão Zinco-Lombador, RECAPE, Volume II – Relatório Base. Retrieved from:
https://siaia.apambiente.pt/AIADOC/RECAPE464/rb_recape1_pez-lombador20171115103829.pdf
- [17] SOMINCOR, 2009. Relatório de Monitorização, Declaração de Impacte Ambiental – Projecto “Mina Neves-Corvo 2007”. Retrieved from:
<https://siaia.apambiente.pt/AIADOC/PA436/relat%C3%B3rio%20anual%20monitoriza%C3%A7%C3%A3o%20-%202009%202019423135552.pdf>
- [18] SNIRH, Dados de Base, Monitorização, Redes, Qualidade Águas Subterrâneas, Bacias Hidrográficas, Guadiana, Águas Subterrâneas, A0Z1RH7 - Zona Sul Portuguesa da Bacia do Guadiana. Retrieved from:
<https://snirh.apambiente.pt/index.php?idMain=2&idItem=1>
- [19] SNIRH, Dados de Base, Monitorização, Redes, Qualidade Águas Subterrâneas, Bacias Hidrográficas, Guadiana. Retrieved from:
<https://snirh.apambiente.pt/index.php?idMain=2&idItem=1>

- [20] Büyük, G., Akça, E., Kume, T., & Nagano, T. (2016). Investigation of Nitrate Pollution in Groundwater Used for Irrigation in Konya-Karapınar Region, Central Anatolia. In KSÜ DoğaBil. Derg (Vol. 19, Issue 2).
- [21] Bozdağ, A. (2015). Combining AHP with GIS for assessment of irrigation water quality in Çumra irrigation district (Konya), Central Anatolia, Turkey. Environmental Earth Sciences, 73(12), 8217–8236. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-014-3972-4>.
- [22] Diri, M. (2018). KONYA KAPALI HAVZASI YÜZEYSEL SU KALİTESİ DEĞİŞİMİNİN İZLENMESİ.
- [23] TÜBİTAK MAM. (2010). HavzaKorumaEylemPlanlarınınHazırlanması - Konya KapalıHavzası.
https://www.tarimorman.gov.tr/SYGM/Belgeler/havza%20koruma%20eylem%20planlar%C4%B1/Konya_Kapali_Havzasi.pdf
- [24] TÜİK (Turkish Statistical Institute). Retrieved July 13, 2022. <https://cip.tuik.gov.tr>
- [25] TÜİK (Turkish Statistical Institute). Retrieved July 7-8, 2022. biruni.tuik.gov.tr/medas
- [26] Kurtkulak, H. (2014). KENTSEL ATIKSULARIN GERİ KAZANIMI VE YEŞİL ALANLARIN SULANMASINDA YENİDEN KULLANIMI: KONYA KENTİ ÖRNEĞİ.
- [27] Aydın, M. E., & Koyuncu, S. (2014). RESTRICTED URBAN REUSE OF KONYA (TURKEY) MUNICIPAL WASTEWATER TREATMENT PLANT EFFLUENTS VIA RECLAIMED WATER DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM Urban Water Management and Water Demand Management.
- [28] KOP BölgeKalkınmaİdaresiBaşkanlığı (Konya Plains Project Regional Development Administration). (2021, August). KOP BölgesiSosyo-EkonomikGöstergeler.<http://www.kop.gov.tr/upload/dokumanlar/273.pdf>
- [29] KOP Bölge Kalkınma İdaresi Başkanlığı. (2014). KOP EylemPlanı.
<http://www.kop.gov.tr/upload/dokumanlar/16.pdf>
- [30] Çelekli, A., Lekesiz, Ö., & Çetin, T. (2021). Eco-Assessment of Streams of Konya Closed River Basin (Turkey) Using Various Ecoregional Diatom Indices.
<https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-998632/v1>

[31] TRAGSATEC, INITEC INFRASTRUCTURES, & SU-YAPI. (2018). Konya Kapalı Havzası Yönetim Planı.

<https://www.tarimorman.gov.tr/SYGM/Belgeler/NHYP%20DEN%C4%B0Z/KONYA%20KAPALI%20NEH%C4%B0R%20HAVZASI%20Y%C3%96NET%C4%B0M%20PLANI.pdf>

[32] WWF. (2014). Konya’da Suyun Bugünü Raporu. Ofset Yayınevi.

https://wwftr.awsassets.panda.org/downloads/konya_da_suyun_bugnu_raporu.pdf

[33] T.C. Kalkınma Bakanlığı Konya Ovası Projesi Bölge Kalkınma İdaresi Başkanlığı. (2014,December). KOP Eylem Planı.

<http://www.kop.gov.tr/upload/dokumanlar/16.pdf>

[34] Hanene Akrou, Ahmed Ghrabi, Thuraya Mellah, Lobna Mansouri, Janire Uribe Asarta, J. Jaime Gómez-Hernández, Ali K. Saysel, Nadim Copty, Leonardo Azevedo, João Lino Pereira, George Karatzas, & Emmanouil Varouchakis. (2022). InTheMED D5.1 Report on Site Characterization and Hot Spot Identification (Version V3). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397472>